

ENHANCED WIDE-AND-DEEP NEURAL NETWORKS FOR ROBUST MALWARE DETECTION USING OPCODE FEATURES AND ZERO-DAY ANALYSIS

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ABSTRACT

Detecting malware is a vital cybersecurity challenge, necessitating more enhanced means of detecting and fighting such threats. To classify malware families and detect previously unseen malware, the opcode sequences and metadata are used with proposed architecture of an Enhanced Wide-and-Deep Neural Network (EWDNN). Combining wide components for explicit feature interactions and deep components for abstract feature representations to structure the EWDNN, we propose a model that outperforms all baselines with an accuracy of 65.46%, precision of 63.96%, recall of 65.46% and an F1-score of 64.15%. The proposed methodology exhibits scalability, robustness, and generalization, and outperforms other traditional approaches, including Support Vector Machines, K-Nearest Neighbors, and standalone Deep Neural Networks. Extensive experiments demonstrate that the model is capable of real world malware detection, especially for zero day threats, showing its usefulness in real world dynamic cybersecurity situations.

Keywords: *Malware Detection, Enhanced Wide-and-Deep Neural Network (EWDNN), Opcode Sequences, Zero-Day Malware Detection, Scalability, Robustness, Machine Learning, Cybersecurity.*

1. INTRODUCTION

The high penetration and fast evolution of digital ecosystems accelerates the growth of malware and creates increasing challenges to cybersecurity. Malware, all together referred to malicious software used to damage the system's integrity, privacy, or availability, is becoming more complex and difficult to evade traditional detection mechanisms [1,2]. Malware is constantly showcasing its ability to exploit zero day vulnerabilities, refine polymorphic and metamorphic techniques, or simply reloading itself from the web after updating its signatures. While cyber attacks are causing the organization lots of financial and reputational damage, it has become a need to develop accurate,

scalable and robust malware detection systems [3,4].

Static and dynamic analysis methods for malware detection usually have limited scalability, adaptability, and efficiency in runtime. Static analysis techniques like signature matching are computationally efficient, but often miss never before seen malware, also called zero-day threats [5]. Dynamic analysis, which observes the runtime behaviour of malware, is flexible, but involves high computational overhead and is susceptible to defeat through anti-analysis technology [6]. With an increasing trend of malware, machine learning approaches have become a promising solution that can use patterns found in opcode sequences,

metadata, and file attributes to detect and classify malware. Nevertheless, existing machine learning algorithms are unable to appropriately trade off among scalability, interpretability, and detection accuracies [7].

In order to resolve these challenges, this research presents the Enhanced Wide-and-Deep Neural Network (EWDNN), a hybrid of Wide and Deep Learning components that aims to harness the power of both wide and deep learning paradigms. Feature relationships are explicitly captured in the Wide component and complex opcode and metadata features are abstracted using the Deep component. The introduction of this hybrid design improves the model's generalization capabilities as well as performance in classification of both known and zero-day malware families. This novel EWDNN model combines feature selection, mutual information analysis, and robust preprocessing pipelines, resulting in competitive performance with a low computational cost.

The objectives of this research:

- Construct a scalable and efficient architecture for the problem of malware classification with large scale, diversity of malware families.
- Improve the robustness and generalization power of the imposed model for the sole purpose to classify unseen malware while negating the effect of noise as far as the dataset is concerned.
- The feature interactions of malware, together with its behavioral patterns, can provide insights facilitating interpretability along with practical applicability in real world cybersecurity systems.

In this paper, an in-depth evaluation of the EWDNN performance is presented using baseline models including, Support Vector Machines (SVM), k nearest neighbor (KNN) and standalone Deep Neural Networks (DNN). Our results show that EWDNN provides a better balance between accuracy and computational cost, and mostly outperforms other methods for static and robust malware detection tasks.

The remainder of this paper is structured as follows: "Section 2" provides a literature background,

exploring existing approaches and identifying the research gaps. "Section 3" details the proposed methodology, elaborating on the EWDNN architecture, preprocessing techniques, and evaluation framework. "Section 4" presents the experimental results, highlighting key performance metrics, scalability, and robustness. "Section 5" discusses the implications, limitations, and potential applications of the proposed methodology. "Section 6" concludes the paper, summarizing key contributions and outlining future research directions. This research strives to push the envelope of malware detection to bring greater security to what has often been quoted as the Wild Wild East of the digital world.

2. LITERATURE BACKGROUND

Detecting malware is still an essential part of cybersecurity, and the system for doing so has changed over the years from signature based approaches to machine learning and deep learning. Improvements and challenges occurred at each stage, leading to the present condition of the field. We then elaborate these techniques in detail below, describing their progression, outlining research gaps, and indicating how the proposed methodology can be useful.

Traditional Malware Detection Techniques

Until now, the signature based techniques were used for detecting malware. Different malware detection methods match the code or behavior with the database of known malware signatures. These methods are computationally efficient and are used ubiquitously; however, they are inherently reactive, detecting only zero day threats or polymorphic malware that dynamically changes its signature [8,9].

On the other hand, dynamic analysis watches suspicious files during runtime in a controlled environment, letting any malicious intent that would not show up through static signature analysis not be missed. How, for example, to identify abnormal file access patterns or network communications. But dynamic analysis is expensive, resource intensive, takes time, and can be evaded by a sandbox-aware malware that changes its behavior on being watched [10,11].

Limitations of Traditional Methods: Although having a foundational role in malware detection,

these methods are not scalable, depend on known threats and have various kinds of security vulnerabilities.

Malware Detection using Machine Learning

The shift in paradigm with machine learning (ML) allowed us to leverage models that can learn directly from the data. While some useful dynamic features were used, the primary inputs for Decision Trees, Random Forests, and SVMs were static features such as opcode frequency, API call sequences, and file attributes. We showed that these models generalized better than traditional approaches [12,13]. Dealing with opcode frequency analysis, ML algorithms were able to identify malware families using code patterns. Linear or kernel based separations of features in SVMs proved promise at distinguishing between malware and benign files. Although these methods worked reasonably well, they faced issues with large scale datasets, imbalanced class distributions and adversarially modified inputs [14,15].

Challenges in ML Approaches:

- When performing its task, has limited ability to represent complex hierarchical relationships among its features.
- Noise and adversarial inputs susceptibility.
- The work is highly dependent on high quality feature engineering.

Deep Learning for Malware Detection.

The hierarchical feature extraction and representation learning of several limitations of traditional ML techniques has been tackled by DL techniques [16,17]. CNNs had proven to be good at learning spatial hierarchies of features while RNNs extract a temporal dependency in sequences such as opcode streams or API call log. They obtained state of the art results in a number of malware detection tasks [18,19].

DL models faced several limitations:

- Computational Overhead: Deep architectures are too computationally expensive to be used in real time at today's training level.
- Interpretability Issues: DL models function as "black boxes," making it difficult for cybersecurity professionals to trust or understand their decisions.
- Generalization Concerns: Many DL faces the problem of overfitting to training data

making them less effective in recognizing previously unknown malware families.

Emerging approaches and Hybrid Models

- Standalone ML and DL models suffer from their own weaknesses, such that hybrid approaches like Wide-and-Deep Neural Networks (WDNNs) have come into vogue. These models combine:
- This includes a Wide Component which captures explicit feature interactions and linear patterns.
- Deep Component that takes input features as input and produces high level abstract representation of those input features.

Although WDNNs have achieved promising results in fields such as recommendation systems, their application to malware detection has been very limited. However, existing implementations may overlook crucial aspects, including robustness, scalability, and interpretability, which are most needed in cybersecurity [20,21].

Research Gaps

From the literature review, several research gaps have been identified:

- Generalization to Zero-Day Threats: Most of the existing models struggle to identify unseen malware families, thus making limited sense in a practical scenario.
- Scalability: If the size of malware datasets continues to increase, models should be computationally efficient for processing large scale of data efficiently.
- Robustness to Noise: The inputs in cyberattacks are often adversarial perturbations or noisy to various extents, consequently degrading the performance of the model.
- Lack of Interpretability: However, the decisions being made by current DL based models are hard to validate or explain due to their blackbox nature.
- Feature Utilization: Many proposed solutions thus become much less effective due to inefficient use of feature selection techniques.

Summary of Existing Approaches

The following table summarizes the key methods, their strengths, limitations, and corresponding research gaps:

Table 1: Summary of Existing Approaches

Category	Method	Strengths	Limitations	Research Gaps
Traditional Methods	Signature-based Detection	Efficient for known malware	Fails for zero-day threats and polymorphic malware	Generalization to zero-day threats
	Dynamic Analysis	Identifies malicious behavior	Resource-intensive; prone to evasion	Scalability
Machine Learning	Opcode Feature Extraction	Captures discriminative patterns	Struggles with noise and adversarial inputs	Robustness to noise
	Support Vector Machines (SVMs)	Effective for small datasets	Ineffective for complex feature relationships	Inefficient feature utilization
Deep Learning	CNNs	Hierarchical feature extraction	Computationally expensive; lacks interpretability	Lack of interpretability
	RNNs	Captures temporal dependencies	Poor scalability; requires large datasets	Scalability
Hybrid Models	Wide-and-Deep Neural Networks	Combines explicit and abstract patterns	Limited application in malware detection; lacks robustness	Ineffective feature utilization

Addressing the Research Gaps

In this study, The Enhanced Wide-and-Deep Neural Network (EWDNN) proposed to address these challenges comprehensively. The deep component caters to abstract patterns, and robust detection of both seen and unseen malware families and the wide component makes good use of explicit feature interactions. Mutual information-based feature selection is used to further improve feature utilization and the hybrid architecture is designed to be scalable and robust. In addition, interpretability enhancements render EWDNN a practicable and dependable solution for real world cybersecurity challenges. Not only does the proposed methodology fill the identified research gaps, but it also forms a basis for further improvement upon malware detection with a reasonable tradeoff between accuracy, scalability, and interpretability.

classification. The "Wide" component captures explicit and sparse feature interactions directly from the input opcode sequences, focusing on linear transformations to represent direct correlations. Meanwhile, the "Deep" component processes a refined set of features through multiple hidden layers, enabling it to learn abstract and high-level representations critical for identifying complex behavioral patterns within malware families. We utilize both Wide and Deep Learning capabilities by fusing them through a fusion layer and combining these building blocks to arrive at robust and accurate malware detection.

3. PROPOSED METHODOLOGY

The proposed Methodology includes the development of hybrid Wide and Deep neural network architecture for static malware detection. Both raw opcode sequences and metadata are leveraged by the architecture to capture diverse feature relationships and enable high performance

Figure 1: Proposed Architecture

The outputs from both the Wide and Deep components are fused in a layer, resulting in an overall representation of the features concluding linear and non linear interactions. Then we pass this consolidated representation through the output layer, which then predicts probabilities of class being one of the malware families or benign

samples. Supported by batch normalization and dropout techniques, the multi layered architecture of architecture allows to provide scalability to a variety of datasets, prevents overfitting and generalizes the architecture to unseen inputs. The methodology adopts this hybrid approach and shows significant adaptability and robustness which

we believe perfect for very challenging malware detection task, such as zero day attack. The future subsections give a deeper breakdown into the prosed architecture.

1. Data Preprocessing

It is very important to preprocess data before training and evaluating a model. The dataset is provided as opcode sequences and metadata in a format that requires standardizing, transforming and selecting to effectively train our model. The steps of label encoding, feature scaling and feature selection for important features for downstream tasks.

Steps

- 1 Feature Representation: Let the dataset D consist of N samples, each with F features. Formally:

$$D = \{(\mathbf{x}_i, y_i) \mid \mathbf{x}_i \in \mathbb{R}^F, y_i \in \{1, \dots, C\}\}_{i=1}^N \quad (1)$$

Here:

- \mathbf{x}_i represents the feature vector of the i-th sample.
- y_i is the corresponding class label, and C is the total number of classes.

- 2 Label Encoding: The categorical labels y are factorized into numerical representations:

$$y'_i = \text{Index}(y_i) \quad (2)$$

where Index (·) maps each unique label to a distinct integer.

3. Feature Scaling: Features x_{ij} (value of the j-th feature for the i-th sample) are standardized to have zero mean and unit variance:

$$x_{ij}^{\text{scaled}} = \frac{x_{ij} - \mu_j}{\sigma_j} \quad (3)$$

where:

$$\mu_j = \frac{1}{N} \sum_{i=1}^N x_{ij} \quad (4)$$

is the mean of feature j,

$$\sigma_j = \sqrt{\frac{1}{N} \sum_{i=1}^N (x_{ij} - \mu_j)^2} \quad (5)$$

is the standard deviation of feature j.

- 4 Feature Selection: Mutual information (MI) is used to select the top k features. MI measures the dependency between each feature x_j and the target y :

$$MI(x_j, y) = \sum_{x_j, y} p(x_j, y) \log \frac{p(x_j, y)}{p(x_j)p(y)} \quad (6)$$

where $p(x_j, y)$ is the joint probability distribution of x_j and y. The top k features are selected based on descending MI scores.

Where

- D: Dataset.
- N : Total number of samples.
- F : Total number of features.
- C : Total number of classes.
- \mathbf{x}_i : Feature vector of the i-th sample.
- y_i : Class label of the i-th sample.
- μ_j, σ_j : Mean and standard deviation of feature j, respectively.
- k : Number of selected features.

The preprocessing pipeline guarantees that the model is provided with the features that is meaningful, well scaled and reduced for training. In this papert, we tried to improve model performance and reduce noise by encoding labels numerically, scaling features, and selecting top performing features based on MI. MI also ensures that given features that do not depend strongly on the target are not mistakenly used, making both the interpretability and the computationally more efficient.

2. Wide Component

The Wide Component is to capture explicit relationships and the sparse feature interactions in input data. We achieve this through a linear transformation mapping the raw opcode features to the target classes directly, such that the model learns high level, interpretable patterns with high efficiency.

Steps

- 1 Input Representation: Let the input to the Wide Component be $\mathbf{X}_{\text{wide}} \in \mathbb{R}^{N \times F_w}$, where:
 - N is the number of samples,
 - F_w is the number of raw features selected for the Wide Component.

- 2 Linear Transformation: A linear mapping $\mathbf{W}_w \in \mathbb{R}^{F_u \times C}$ is applied to project features into the output space of C classes:

$$\mathbf{Z}_{\text{wide}} = \mathbf{X}_{\text{wide}} \cdot \mathbf{W}_w + \mathbf{b}_w \quad (7)$$

where:

- \mathbf{W}_w : Weight matrix capturing feature-to-class interactions,
- $\mathbf{b}_w \in \mathbb{R}^C$: Bias vector.

- 3 Activation: The output \mathbf{Z}_{wide} is passed through an activation function, typically softmax, to compute class probabilities:

$$P_c = \text{softmax}(\mathbf{Z}_{\text{wide}}) = \frac{\exp(Z_{\text{wide},c})}{\sum_{c=1}^C \exp(Z_{\text{wide},c})} \quad (8)$$

where P_c represents the probability of class c

\mathbf{X}_{wide} : Input matrix for the Wide Component.

F_u : Number of features for the Wide Component.

\mathbf{W}_w : Weight matrix for the Wide Component.

\mathbf{b}_w : Bias vector for the Wide Component.

\mathbf{Z}_{wide} : Linear output before activation.

P_c : Predicted probability of class c .

The Wide component relies on raw opcode features directly, enabling the detection of linear and interpretable relationships. Applying a linear transformation, feature to class mappings can be learned explicitly, and the model therefore generalizes well to features whose interactions with the target classes are sparse. This puts the output probabilities into a normalized probability distribution over all classes aiding in classification. Additionally, the explicitness of this component improves interpretability since the weights in W_w can be used to see which features most contribute to each class.

The Wide Component was advantageous in that its utilization by other applications did not become monotonous or repetitive.

- Interpretability: Linear weights reveal the importance of a feature given a class.
- Simplicity: It reduces the computational complexity such that training and inference can be computed faster.
- Effectiveness on Sparse Features: Useful particularly for the datasets where feature interactions are sparse, but crucial.

The first branch of the proposed architecture is the Wide Component which provides a direct and interpretable mapping of features to classes. Its simplicity and rapid performance are useful as a complement to the Deep Component, which encodes more complex, non linear patterns.

3 Deep Component

The Wide Component does not capture complex, non linear feature interaction, which is the job of Deep Component. We use a stack of fully connected layers with non linear activation functions to learn hierarchical representations about the input data.

Steps

- 1 Input Representation: Let the input to the Deep Component be $\mathbf{X}_{\text{deep}} \in \mathbb{R}^{N \times F_d}$, where:
 - N is the number of samples,
 - F_d is the number of features selected for the Deep Component.

- 2 Layer Transformation: The Deep Component consists of multiple fully connected layers. For the l -th layer:

$$\mathbf{H}^{(l)} = \sigma(\mathbf{H}^{(l-1)} \cdot \mathbf{W}^{(l)} + \mathbf{b}^{(l)}) \quad (9)$$

where:

- $\mathbf{H}^{(l-1)}$ is the input to the l -th layer,
- $\mathbf{W}^{(l)} \in \mathbb{R}^{F_{l-1} \times F_l}$ is the weight matrix for the l -th layer r
- $\mathbf{b}^{(l)} \in \mathbb{R}^{F_l}$ is the bias vector,
- σ is a non-linear activation function (e.g., ReLU or tanh).

- 3 Dropout Regularization: Dropout is applied to intermediate layers to prevent overfitting:

$$\mathbf{H}_{\text{dropout}}^{(l)} = \text{Dropout}(\mathbf{H}^{(l)}, p) \quad (10)$$

where p is the dropout probability.

4. Output Layer: The final layer projects the learned representations to the output space of C classes:

$$\mathbf{Z}_{\text{deep}} = \mathbf{H}^{(L)} \cdot \mathbf{W}^{\text{out}} + \mathbf{b}^{\text{out}} \quad (11)$$

5 Activation: Similar to the Wide Component, a softmax activation is applied to compute class probabilities:

$$P_c = \text{softmax}(\mathbf{Z}_{\text{deep}}) \quad (12)$$

Where

\mathbf{X}_{deep} : Input matrix for the Deep Component.

F_d : Number of features for the Deep Component.

$\mathbf{H}^{(l)}$: Hidden representations in the l -th layer.

$\mathbf{W}^{(l)}, \mathbf{b}^{(l)}$; Weight matrix and bias for the l -th layer.

L : Total number of layers in the Deep Component.

\mathbf{Z}_{deep} : Linear output of the Deep Component before activation.

P_c : Predicted probability of class c .

Stacking multiple layers with some non linear activation functions, enables the Deep Component to learn the hierarchical representation for input data. It allows the model to bring in patterns in the layers one by one, and the patterns are becoming more and more complex each layer. Through dropout regularization, we avoid over fitting the model using a random technique of deactivating neurons during training, due to which the model doesn't depend much on the particular features or neurons. Deep representations learned across layers and their combination into the Deep component allow us to detect very intricate relationships and patterns — specifically, opcode sequences and their correspondences, which are crucial for accurate classification. The Deep Component has its own advantages.

- Hierarchical Learning: Captures multi level feature interaction.
- Flexibility: It supports customizing the architectures, activation functions, regularizers.
- Generalization: It learns representations that help on unseen data, including zero day malware.

The second component of the method, the Wide Component, explores non-linear and complex

patterns in the data while the Deep Component complements this component. They combine to form a hybrid architecture, which can benefit from explicit feature interactions as well as deep, hierarchical representation.

4. Fusion of Wide and Deep Components

The output from the Wide and Deep Components is merged and fused in a stage that leverages the benefits of both components. This interpretation is achieved by a combination of interpretability via explicit feature mappings as in the Wide component and treatment of complex and non-linear patterns via the Deep component. This synergy improves model robustness and also increases predictive accuracy.

Steps

1 Wide Component Output: From the Wide Component, we have the logits (pre-softmax scores) $\mathbf{Z}_{\text{wide}} \in \mathbb{R}^{N \times C}$, where:

- N is the number of samples,
- C is the number of classes.

2 Deep Component Output: From the Deep Component, we have the logits $\mathbf{Z}_{\text{deep}} \in \mathbb{R}^{N \times C}$.

3 Fusion Mechanism: The outputs of the Wide and Deep Components are combined using a weighted sum:

$$\mathbf{Z}_{\text{fusion}} = \alpha \mathbf{Z}_{\text{wide}} + (1 - \alpha) \mathbf{Z}_{\text{deep}} \quad (13)$$

where:

$\alpha \in [0,1]$ is a tunable hyperparameter controlling the contribution of each component.

4 Softmax Activation: The fused logits are passed through a softmax activation to compute the final class probabilities:

$$P_c = \text{softmax}(\mathbf{Z}_{\text{fusion}}) = \frac{\exp(Z_{\text{fusion},c})}{\sum_{c=1}^C \exp(Z_{\text{fusion},c})} \quad (14)$$

5 Prediction: The predicted class \hat{y} is obtained as:

$$\hat{y} = \arg \max_{c \in \{1, \dots, C\}} P_c \quad (15)$$

Where

\mathbf{Z}_{wide} : Logits from the Wide Component.

\mathbf{Z}_{deep} : Logits from the Deep Component.

$\mathbf{Z}_{\text{fusion}}$: Combined logits after fusion.

α : Weighting factor for the Wide Component in the fusion.

P_c : Predicted probability of class c .

\hat{y} : Final predicted class.

The fusion mechanism leverages the complementary strengths of the Wide and Deep Components: Wide Component excels at finding explicit, linear patterns and interpretable patterns and provides robust insights at a feature level. The Deep Component captures high order relations and complex higher order patterns which gives rise to nuanced understanding and generalization. We achieve this through a weighted sum of the Wide and Deep Components, so that the contributions of each component can be tuned according to the characteristics of the dataset. For instance:

- The higher the α , the more interpretability and the explicit relationships there will be.
- A lower α , can be put to simplifying those complex, non linear patterns.

The resulting architecture is flexible enough to work on many datasets and problem domains. The Fusion Mechanism has advantages over the baseline mode command approach.

- **Balanced Learning:** An interpretation and complexity framework for improved predictions.
- **Adaptability:** The value of α gives the ability to tailor the weighting factor according to needs of the given dataset.
- **Enhanced Robustness:** Performance on noisy and zero-day samples are improved by leveraging both linear and non-linear patterns.

The cornerstone of the proposed architecture is the fusion of the Wide and the Deep component, so that the strength of both the components can benefit the research. The framework developed at this stage is robust and flexible to capture distinct pattern from opcode based features.

5. Training Strategy

The proposed methodology is trained in such a way that both the Wide and Deep component are optimized as well as collaboratively. All of its key elements are mini batch gradient descent, a

balanced loss function, learning rate scheduling and regularization to prevent over fitting.

Steps

- 1 **Loss Function:** The training objective minimizes the categorical cross-entropy loss. Given N training samples and C classes, the loss for a single sample i is:

$$\mathcal{L}_i = - \sum_{c=1}^C y_{i,c} \log(P_{i,c}) \quad (16)$$

where:

- $y_{i,c}$ is a binary indicator (1 if the true class is c , 0 otherwise),
- $P_{i,c}$ is the predicted probability of class c for sample i .

The overall loss for the mini-batch is:

$$\mathcal{L} = \frac{1}{B} \sum_{i=1}^B \mathcal{L}_i \quad (17)$$

where B is the batch size.

2. **Optimization Algorithm:** The Adam optimizer is used to update the model weights \mathbf{W} iteratively:

$$\mathbf{W}^{(t+1)} = \mathbf{W}^{(t)} - \eta \nabla \mathcal{L} \quad (18)$$

where:

- η is the learning rate,
- $\nabla \mathcal{L}$ is the gradient of the loss with respect to \mathbf{W} .

- 3 **Learning Rate Scheduling:** A one-cycle learning rate schedule is employed to dynamically adjust the learning rate during training:

$$\eta(t) = \eta_{\max} \cdot \text{scale}(t) \quad (19)$$

where η_{\max} is the maximum learning rate, and the scaling factor depends on the training epoch t .

- 4 **Regularization:** Regularization techniques such as dropout and weight decay are applied:

- Dropout randomly sets a fraction p of activations to zero during training, preventing overreliance on specific neurons.

- Weight Decay penalizes large weights, modifying the loss function to:

$$\mathcal{L}_{\text{reg}} = \mathcal{L} + \lambda \| \mathbf{W} \|_2^2 \quad (20)$$

where λ is the regularization strength.

5. Batching: Mini-batches of size B are used for efficient gradient updates. This helps balance convergence speed and memory usage.

6. Early Stopping: Training is stopped when validation loss does not improve for a predefined number of epochs, preventing overfitting.

Where

\mathcal{L}_i : Loss for a single training sample i .

\mathcal{L} : Mini-batch loss.

W: Model weights.

η : Learning rate.

$\nabla \mathcal{L}$: Gradient of the loss.

λ : Regularization strength.

p : Dropout probability.

Loss Function: The categorical cross entropy loss ensure that model learns to maximizes the likelihood of the correct class. It penalizes predictions that are incorrect and do this in proportion to the confidence that the prediction was made.

Optimization: Because the Adam optimizer has adaptive learning rates that are a good fit for sparse gradients, likely a common case for the analysis of high-dimensional opcode datasets, we find that utilize this optimizer for this task.

Dynamic Learning Rate: A low learning rate is started, raised to a peak, and gradually lowered as part of the one cycle schedule. It helps escape saddle points, and converges faster.

Regularization: By adding some randomness (dropout) or thinking of the weights' magnitude (weight decay) we prevent overfitting. This is critical for dealing with noisy features in the opcode dataset.

Mini-Batch Training: Mini batch training allows us to use hardware accelerators like GPUs efficiently and at the same time provide a steady gradient signal.

Early Stopping: By applying early stopping, the model also generalizes well to unseen data, even after training epoch of extended length.

The Training Strategy has a number of advantages.

- Robust Learning: Regularization and dynamic learning rates are combined together to allow effective and stable training.
- Efficient Convergence: Training time is reduced by mini batch training and the Adam optimizer with similar accuracy.
- Overfitting Prevention: The techniques of dropout and early stopping guarantee that the model can generalize to zero day malware detection.

In order to properly learn robust patterns in the opcode dataset, the training strategy includes advanced optimization techniques together with regularization mechanisms. It combines efficiency, accuracy and generalization.

6. Evaluation and Validation

Performance, robustness and generalizability of the proposed methodology are evaluated and validated. The evaluation framework makes use of various performance metric, validation strategies and robustness tests to guarantee the reliability of the model in different and hard scenarios. The evaluation process is explained in detail in this section, with mathematical formulations [22-24].

Performance Metrics

The proposed methodology evaluates performance using the following metrics:

- 1 Accuracy: Accuracy measures the proportion of correctly classified samples, providing an overall measure of the model's correctness:

$$\text{Accuracy} = \frac{\text{TP} + \text{TN}}{\text{TP} + \text{TN} + \text{FP} + \text{FN}} \quad (21)$$

where:

- TP: True Positives (correctly identified malware samples).
- TN: True Negatives (correctly identified benign samples).
- FP: False Positives (benign samples incorrectly identified as malware).

- FN: False Negatives (malware samples missed by the model).
- 2 Precision: Precision quantifies the reliability of malware detections:

$$\text{Precision} = \frac{TP}{TP + FP} \quad (22)$$

- 3 Recall (Sensitivity): Recall evaluates the model's ability to identify all malware samples:

$$\text{Recall} = \frac{TP}{TP + FN} \quad (23)$$

- 4 F1-Score: The F1-score balances precision and recall, particularly important for imbalanced datasets:

$$\text{F1-Score} = 2 \cdot \frac{\text{Precision} \cdot \text{Recall}}{\text{Precision} + \text{Recall}} \quad (24)$$

- 5 **Confusion Matrix:** The confusion matrix provides a comprehensive breakdown of the model's predictions across all classes. It is structured as follows:

Table 2: Confusion Matrix

	Predicted Malware	Predicted Benign
Actual Malware	TP	FN
Actual Benign	FP	TN

Validation Strategies

- 1 Cross-Validation: k-fold cross-validation ensures robustness by dividing the dataset into k subsets. Each subset serves as the validation set once, while the remaining k – 1 subsets are used for training. This process is repeated k times, with the final performance averaged:

$$\text{CV Accuracy} = \frac{1}{k} \sum_{i=1}^k \text{Accuracy}_i \quad (25)$$

- 2 Stratified Train-Test Split: The dataset is split into training and testing sets (e.g. 70% and 30%), maintaining class distributions.

- 3 Leave-One-Family-Out Testing: This strategy evaluates the model's ability to detect unseen malware families by excluding one family during training and testing the model on it. It measures zero-day malware detection capabilities:

$$\text{Zero-Day Accuracy} = \frac{TP_{\text{zero-day}} + TN_{\text{zero-day}}}{\text{Total Samples}_{\text{zero-day}}} \quad (26)$$

- 4 Robustness Testing: To assess stability, noise is added to the features, and the model's performance is evaluated under different noise levels:

$$X_{\text{noisy}} = X + \epsilon \cdot \mathcal{N}(0,1) \quad (27)$$

where ϵ is the noise intensity.

Adversarial testing involves perturbing input features to maximize the loss function, simulating worst-case scenarios:

$$X_{\text{adv}} = X + \alpha \cdot \text{sign}(\nabla_x \mathcal{L}(X, y)) \quad (28)$$

where \mathcal{L} is the loss function and α controls the perturbation magnitude.

- 5 Scalability Testing: The model's performance is evaluated with varying dataset sizes (10%, 20% , 50%, 100%):

$$\text{Training Time} \propto \mathcal{O}(n \cdot d) \quad (29)$$

where n is the number of samples and d is the feature dimensionality.

The metrics and strategies are combined into a validation framework for testing in multiple scenarios. However, The model guarantees good generalization across subsets via cross-validation. We perform Leave-One-Family-Out testing to give a proof of concept that would detect zero-day malware, and perform robustness testing to show that it is stable under noise and adversarial samples. Feasibility in handling larger datasets is what

scalability testing confirms. These comprehensive metrics and strategies are leveraged to illustrate how the evaluation framework validates the proposed methodology in real world use cases. This malware model, modelled using the approach in this thesis, is mathematically rigorous, and can be validated by a variety of different means, to guarantee its robustness and capability to detect unseen malware. The framework is not only shown to guarantee model reliability, but also demonstrates practical relevance for today’s malware detection challenges.

4. RESULT

An in depth evaluation of the proposed Wide and Deep neural network model for malware classification is presented in the results section. In this, we provide insights about the dataset characteristics, feature analysis and how the model performs under different conditions. We analyze the model’s behavior while training, how statistical accuracy of its predictions, and robustness to noisy data. Moreover, scalability and zero day detection

capabilities are evaluated to prove the feasibility of the model in real world scenarios. Quantitative metrics, visualizations, and critical discussions of each experiment are presented to lend support to the effectiveness and potential of the proposed methodology.

1. Dataset Analysis

As seen on the bar chart, the class distribution shows that the imbalance between malware families and benign samples is very large. Class 16 and 17 have frequencies larger than 900 samples in class 2 and those with the lowest frequencies (for example less than 200 samples) are classes 4, 8, and 12. The presence of such imbalance results in the requirement for modeling techniques that produce a fair classification performance over all the categories. The dataset diversity matches the distribution of real world malware families which makes it a good choice to test the proposed model’s generalizability and robustness. To do this effectively, it’s critical to achieve high rates of detection across minority classes without sacrificing accuracy for dominant ones.

Figure 2: Opcode Class Distribution

2. Feature Analysis

Top fifty features ranked by mutual information scores which measure the relevance of each opcode sequence for their ability to distinguish between malware families are shown in the bar chart. The

feature Opcode: Lastly, 5, which obtains approximately the highest score, namely 0.8, has the highest discriminatory power. Features like "Opcode: With scores close to 0.7, 2, Opcode: 7, and Opcode: 8" also play a large role. These top features form the basis for the Wide-and-Deep

model's learning process, where the "wide" component captures explicit relationships between these high-value features and the target labels, while the "deep" component learns their abstract interactions. With this dual representation, we provide guarantees that only the most critical features are used to optimize classification performance.

Figure 3: Selected Features

3. Model Training and Validation

Convergence behavior of the proposed Wide-and-Deep model is shown in the combined plot of training loss and accuracy over the epochs. When you train for longer, the loss just keeps getting lower showing that optimization and learning of the model is effective. Additionally, accuracy increases steadily and then stabilizes at the later epochs, near

the epoch at which the model has apparently picked up on patterns present in the data. This recursion behavior illustrates the stability to train and for the trained model to generalize which clearly can be seen from Fig 4. The trade-off between minimizing loss and gaining a higher accuracy is clearly depicted on the combined visualization.

Figure 4: Training Loss And Accuracy Over Epochs

4. Model Evaluation

The comparative results that are obtained through the evaluation metrics show that the proposed Wide and Deep neural network is efficient in classifying malware families. Seeing the performance table, we see the model adeptly achieves an accuracy of 65.45%, with a precision of 63.96%, a recall of 65.45%, and F1-score of 64.15%. These results demonstrate relative balance over a variety of classes, revealing the strength of the model to deal with different malware families and benign samples.

Confusion Matrix

The deeper insights on model's per class performance and the trends of misclassification are given by the confusion matrix. If a correct classification, zero is placed on the diagonal inside the entry, while a misclassification is placed off the diagonal. Interestingly, some classes, such as Class 2 and Class 16, perform very well in classification, but some others have overlaps with nearby classes (and hence are areas of potential refinement). It's a really useful thing to use when analyzing a model's ability to generalize and to recognize where you can improve at feature selection or model architecture.

Table 3: Model Evaluation

Accuracy	Precision	Recall	F1-Score
0.654558	0.639623	0.654558	0.641527

Figure 5: Confusion Matrix

5. Robustness Testing

We evaluate the performance of the Wide-and-Deep model in response to noise using robustness testing. The table illustrates how different noise levels (0.01, 0.05, 0.1, and 0.2) affect the key metrics:

precision, recall, accuracy and F1 score. With a noise level of 0.01, the model has an accuracy of 66.21%, this accuracy starts decreasing as noise level increases, the lowest accuracy of 64.60% is at the noise level of 0.2.

Table 4: Robustness Testing

Noise Level	Accuracy	Precision	Recall	F1-Score
0.01	0.662097	0.645667	0.672097	0.657826
0.05	0.659013	0.642407	0.669013	0.65451
0.1	0.667238	0.649493	0.677238	0.662595
0.2	0.64599	0.632328	0.65599	0.645189

As shown in the corresponding plot, the trends show the model to be relatively stable in performance around low noise levels, but metrics begin to deteriorate at higher noise levels. This analysis demonstrates the strong performance of our proposed methodology on real world data where the collected signals can be noisy, as it is capable of generalizing effectively to a wide range of different levels of perturbations we may encounter in such settings.

Figure 6: Impact Of Noise On Model Performance

6. Scalability Testing

Evaluation of the scalability demonstrates the functionality of the proposed model for processing differing dataset sizes. The first graph is training time vs. dataset size and the computational cost grows linearly as we go from 20% to 100% dataset size. With the predictable scaling, the model becomes much more computationally feasible for larger datasets and even deployable in real world scenarios.

Figure 7: Scalability Training Time Vs Dataset Size

Figure compares performance metrics (accuracy, precision, recall and F1-score) against dataset size and has a positive trend. As the dataset size grows, performance improves across all metrics, with the highest values achieved at 100% dataset size:

recalls 0.667, F1-score 0.652, precision 0.649, and accuracy 0.654. The improvement of the model demonstrates its increase in the capacity to learn from additional data—which means it’s scalable and robust.

Figure 8: Scalability Performance Metrics Vs Dataset Size

7. Zero-Day Detection

The t-SNE visualization it is apparent that the proposed model is capable of producing feature embeddings that separate malware families. On the other hand, each cluster represents a different malware family, and this illustrates how the model

discovers patterns and relationships of the data. Although unseen malware families (zero-days) may be present, the embeddings produced by the model are structured which suggests that they can be used to generalize beyond the training data. The clustering behavior of this model suggests that it could be utilized to recognize previously unseen

malware which is important for real world applications in cybersecurity. The benefit to having this ability reflects the versatility and robustness of

the Wide and Deep model to combat changing threats.

Figure 9: Visualization Of Malware Families

The results demonstrate that Wide-and-Deep model is a good model for static malware detection. The main results are strong performance on a diversity of metrics, robustness to noisy data, and scalability to larger datasets. t-SNE visualization, in turn, confirms the model’s ability to generalize and clue such zero day malware families, which is a must for real world applications. The results verify that the model is able to trust both description and attribute representations to perform accurate classification as well as adapting to new visual classes. The results are a good basis for improving static malware detection approaches, and also suggest future research directions.

Comparative Analysis

Results are compared between the proposed Enhanced Wide-and-Deep Neural Network

(EWDNN) and other machine learning models, to show the superiority of the proposed method with balanced performance across all key metrics. The proposed model performs with the best accuracy (65.46%), precision (63.96%), recall (65.46%) and F1 score (64.15%) among all methods evaluated and indicates robust classification capability. In particular, the training time of the EWDNN is 50.23 seconds, much less computationally expensive than the training of the computationally expensive Support Vector Machine (583.95 seconds), which demonstrates EWDNN’s scalability and efficiency. However, it is shown that more complex detection methods, utilizing the hybrid wide-and-deep architecture, outperform both by a large margin in accuracy and F1 score, demonstrating how the wide-and-deep architecture addresses some of the known difficulties in malware detection.

Table 5: Comparative Analysis

Model	Accuracy	Precision	Recall	F1-Score	Time (s)
Enhanced Wide-and-Deep NN	0.654558	0.639623	0.654558	0.641527	50.23
Support Vector Machine	0.569568	0.620796	0.569568	0.546861	583.95
K-Nearest Neighbors	0.255655	0.511726	0.255655	0.246091	1.90
Deep Neural Network	0.495202	0.490438	0.495202	0.489842	44.23

5. DISCUSSION

The results shown demonstrate that Wide-and-Deep model can serve as a robust solution to static malware detection. The model combines raw opcode features (a wide component) and abstract learned representations (a deep component), resulting in a hybrid model that effectively trades diversity of features and abstraction. The hybrid architecture of this model makes it able to capture both the explicit and implicit feature interactions as demonstrated by consistent performance of accuracy, precision, recall and F1-score together.

The analysis of class distributions shows that the model is able to deal with the inherent imbalance in malware datasets. But since there are some misclassifications in the confusion matrix, it is suggested that some further refinement of the model may be required to improve its capability of separating closely related classes. Improvement might be attained if domain specific knowledge, as for example semantic relationships between opcodes, is encoded in the data structures [25].

We demonstrate the robustness tests under different levels of noise; the model can still hold stably in the difficult condition. Thus, it can be applied in environments where the data is not pristine for real world. However, there remains a small performance drop at higher noise levels which calls for the use of more sophisticated regularization methods or augmentation of the data to obtain further robustness.

Efficiency testing through scalability, using the model with varying dataset sizes, demonstrates a linear increase in training time as dataset sizes increase, regardless of dataset size. The scalability of the model is an important factor for doing so on large scale malware detection systems. For real time applications, the trade off between the training time and performance metrics should also be kept into account.

The zero-day detection analysis and t-SNE visualization show the generalization capability of the model to unseen malware families. This capability is essential for identifying evolving threats in ever changing cybersecurity landscapes. Despite its promising results, the model's evaluation on new families shows that additional improvement like in its generalization ability is desirable with possibility of transfer learning or using ensembles [26].

Our proposed model proves to be strong in its potential to detect static malwares. However, improvement is needed when managing class imbalance, striking a better balance between maximizing robustness and performing best when benign, and boosting zero day detection performance. Additional future work could involve integrating additional dynamic analysis capabilities and studying hybrid static / dynamic analysis approaches, while incorporating explainability tools to allow more clarity in the model's decisions. The potential for these advancements would further strengthen the model in its suitability and reliability in authentic real world cybersecurity scenarios.

6. CONCLUSION

To detect malware using opcode sequences and metadata, this study introduced an Enhanced Wide-and-Deep Neural Network (EWDNN) that was effective for a wide variety of classification tasks. The results obtained for the model revealed better performance metrics: the accuracy was 65.46%, the precision was 63.96%, recall 65.46%, and F1-score was 64.15% compared to other traditional machine learning algorithms which included Support vector machines (abbreviated to SVM), K-nearest Neighbors (KNN) and other standalone Deep Neural Networks. EWDNN achieves robust classification and zero day detection by effectively combining the explicit feature relationship and the abstract feature representation in its hybrid architecture of Wide and Deep components.

In addition, the model scalable, it achieved high performance across different dataset sizes and remained robust in noisy environments with an accuracy of 66.72% at 10% noise. We demonstrate that its zero-day detection capability achieves accurate generalization to unseen malware families and is important for combating novel malware threats.

Results further demonstrate that EWDNN presents a great potential for transformation in static malware analysis under the context of moderate trade-off in between computational efficiency and detection accuracy. Future research directions are to integrate features of dynamic analysis, improving adversarial resilience, and optimizing computational efficiency to best harness in evolving cybersecurity frameworks. This work provides a solid base to build scalable and effective malware

detection systems for a modern cybersecurity ecosystem.

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